

Supplementary Figures for “The lungfish—Fish, Amphibian, or Something Else?”

Matthew Cserhati

matthew.cserhati@cui.edu

Supplementary Figure 1. Elbow plot showing the total within sum of squares value per number of clusters (putative baramins). Starting from $k = 6$ clusters there appears to be distortion in the data.

Supplementary Figure 8. Silhouette plot showing an average silhouette value of 0.5 for eight clusters.